

On lactosyl thioureides : synthesis of certain *S*-hepta-*O*-acetyl lactosyl-1-arylisothiocarbamides

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Several *S*-hepta-*O*-acetyl lactosyl-1-arylisothiocarbamides have been synthesized by the interaction of arylthiocarbamides and hepta-*O*-acetyl lactosyl bromide. The identities of these newly synthesized compounds have been established on the basis of usual chemical transformations and IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and mass spectral studies.

In view of applications of the *S*-lactosylated compounds in medicinal chemistry, industries and in many other ways^{1,2} it appeared interesting to carry out synthesis of *S*-lactosyl thioureides. In the present communication seven *S*-hepta-*O*-acetyl lactosyl-1-arylisothiocarbamides (**3**) have been reported. These were prepared by the interaction of hepta-*O*-acetyl lactosyl bromide (**1**) and arylthiocarbamides (**2**) (Scheme 1).

where, R = (a) phenyl, (b) *o*-Cl-phenyl, (c) *m*-Cl-phenyl, (d) *p*-Cl-phenyl, (e) *o*-tolyl, (f) *m*-tolyl, (g) *p*-tolyl

Ac = COCH₃
Scheme 1

Results and discussion

Isopropanolic (30 ml) suspension of hepta-*O*-acetyl lactosyl bromide (0.01 *M*, 7 g) and phenylthiocarbamide (0.01 *M*, 1.5 g) was heated on water bath at about 70°C until the suspension get cleared. The clear solution was then kept at room temperature for 18 h. It was mixed with 100 ml distilled water. This aqueous solution was acidic and non-desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution.

The aqueous solution when treated with NH₄OH afforded a sticky mass which was not solidified on standing for several hours. This sticky mass was failed to afford solid when triturated several times with petroleum ether. The sticky mass was purified by ethanol and water and the solid was obtained m.p. 121°C. It gave charring test and was non-

desulphurisable. Its specific rotation was found $[\alpha]_D^{27} -214.28^\circ$ (*c*, 0.980 in CHCl₃).

The IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, mass³ spectral analysis (Experimental) and elemental analysis (Table 1) clearly indicated the product assign the structure as *S*-hepta-*O*-acetyl lactosyl-1-phenyl isothiocarbamide (**3a**).

When the interaction of hepta-*O*-acetyl lactosyl bromide was extended to other arylthiocarbamides the related *S*-hepta-*O*-acetyl lactosyl-1-arylisothiocarbamides (**3b-g**) were obtained.

Experimental

All melting points recorded are found uncorrected. The structures of newly synthesized compounds are confirmed on the basis of elemental and spectral analysis. IR spectra of the compounds were recorded in KBr on a FTIR Perkin-Elmer (4000–450 cm⁻¹) spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra are run on Bruker DRX-300 instrument operating at 300 MHz and 75 MHz respectively using CDCl₃ solution with TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on Jeol SX-102 FAB instrument. Specific rotation⁴ were recorded on digital polarimeter.

The required hepta-*O*-acetyl lactosyl bromide⁵ and arylthiocarbamides⁶ were prepared by the methods described earlier.

*Hepta-O-acetyl lactosyl bromide*⁷ : (1) m.p. 130°C; IR (KBr) 2967 (C–H), 1751 (C=O), 1223 (C–O), 1066 (C–H, lactose unit), 600 cm⁻¹ (C–Br); ¹H NMR δ 5.5–3.8 (14H, m, lactose unit), 2.1–1.9 ppm (21H, m, 7OAc); ¹³C NMR δ 20.7 (7MeCO), 77.12–60.8 (lactose unit), 170.1–169.1 ppm (7CO); MS (*m/z*) 699 (M⁺+1), 619, 559, 457, 331, 229, 169, 109.

Table I. Interaction of hepta-*O*-acetyl lactosyl bromide (0.01 *M*, 7.00 g) and arylthiocarbamides (0.01 *M*) in isopropanol

Sr. no.	Arylthiocarbamides	<i>S</i> -Hepta- <i>O</i> -acetyl lactosyl-1-aryl isothiocarbamides yield (g)	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Analysis (%) : Found/(Requires)		[α] ²⁷ _D (c in CHCl ₃)
					N	S	
1.	Phenyl- (1.52)	-phenyl- (3a) (4.0)	121	51.81	3.46 (3.63)	3.90 (4.15)	-214.28 (0.980)
2.	<i>o</i> -Cl-phenyl- (1.85)	- <i>o</i> -Cl-phenyl- (3b) (4.0)	140–142	49.62	3.66 (3.48)	4.09 (3.98)	-57.72 (0.693)
3.	<i>m</i> -Cl-phenyl- (1.85)	- <i>m</i> -Cl-phenyl- (3c) (1.7)	120	21.09	3.29 (3.48)	3.59 (3.98)	-152.12 (0.986)
4.	<i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl- (1.85)	- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl- (3d) (1.2)	126	14.88	3.56 (3.48)	4.09 (3.98)	-101.85 (1.080)
5.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl- (1.66)	- <i>o</i> -tolyl- (3e) (3.0)	134–135	38.16	3.33 (3.57)	4.18 (4.08)	-51.75 (0.966)
6.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl- (1.66)	- <i>m</i> -tolyl- (3f) (2.5)	127	31.80	3.25 (3.57)	4.16 (4.08)	-19.88 (1.006)
7.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl- (1.66)	- <i>p</i> -tolyl- (3g) (1.2)	145	15.26	3.44 (3.57)	4.19 (4.08)	-182.69 (1.040)

Satisfactory C, H analysis were obtained for all the compounds.

(3a) m.p. 121°C; [α]²⁷_D -214.28° (c, 0.980 in CHCl₃); IR (KBr) 3350 (N-H), 2970 (Ar-H), 1751 (C=O), 1635 (C=N), 1439 (C-N), 1229 (C-O), 1050 (C-H def. lactose unit), 758 cm⁻¹ (C-S); ¹H NMR δ 7.6–6.8 (5H, m, Ar-H), 5.6–5.3 (2H, s, NH), 5.3–3.4 (14H, m, lactose unit), 2.1–1.9 ppm (2H, m, 7OAc); ¹³C NMR δ 20.8 (7MeCO), 77.7–61.0 (lactose unit), 130.5–120.5 (aromatic), 170.3–169.3 ppm (7CO); MS (*m/z*) 771 (M⁺+1), 711, 669, 619, 559, 331, 229, 169, 109 (Found : C, 51.37; H, 5.35; N, 3.46; S, 3.9. C₃₃H₄₂O₁₇N₂S requires : C, 51.42; H, 5.45; N, 3.63; S, 4.15%).

(3b) m.p. 140–142°C; [α]²⁷_D -57.72° (c, 0.693 in CHCl₃); IR (KBr) 3348 (N-H), 2965 (Ar-H), 1751 (C=O), 1636 (C=N), 1437 (C-N), 1229 (C-O), 1051 (C-H def. lactose), 759 cm⁻¹ (C-S); ¹H NMR δ 7.5–7.0 (4H, m, Ar-H), 6.5–6.1 (2H, s, N-H), 5.4–3.8 (14H, m, lactose unit), 2.1–1.9 ppm (21H, m, 7OAc); ¹³C NMR δ 20.8 (7MeCO), 77.65–61.02 (lactose unit), 134.1–122.2 (aromatic), 170.5–169.3 ppm (7CO); MS (*m/z*) 805 (M⁺+1), 745, 619, 559, 331, 229, 169, 109 (Found : C, 49.16; H, 5.01; N, 3.66; S, 4.09. C₃₃H₄₁O₁₇N₂SCl requires : C, 49.25; H, 5.09; N, 3.48; S, 3.98%).

(3e) m.p. 134–135°C; [α]²⁷_D -51.75° (c, 0.966 in CHCl₃); IR (KBr) 3458 (N-H), 2969 (Ar-H), 1751 (C=O), 1642 (C=N), 1437 (C-N), 1228 (C-O), 1050 (C-H def. lactose), 755 cm⁻¹ (C-S); ¹H NMR δ 7.2–6.9 (4H, m, Ar-H), 5.3–5.2 (2H, s, N-H), 5.2–3.7 (14H, m, lactose unit), 2.2–1.9 (21H, m, 7OAc), 1.2–1.1 ppm (3H, m, Ar-CH₃); ¹³C NMR δ 20.8 (7MeCO), 77.69–61.0 (lactose unit), 130.2–120.1 (aromatic), 170.2–169.3 ppm (7CO); MS (*m/z*) 785 (M⁺+1), 725, 683, 619, 559, 331, 229, 169, 109 (Found : C, 52.12; H, 5.49; N, 3.33; S, 4.18. C₃₄H₄₄O₁₇N₂S requires : C, 52.04; H, 5.61; N, 3.57; S, 4.08%).

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